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Interaction on the diet and substrate on the growth of *Archachatina marginata* in breeding

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Abstract

Nine hundred juveniles of *Archachatina marginata* aged about two weeks, with an average live weight of 2.25 g with an average shell length of 20.12mm were monitored in culture for six (6) months on five types of substrates [S₁ (soil collected in a cassava plantation: *Manihot* sp.), S₂ (S₁ with 10% oyster shell meal), S₃ (S₁ with 10% sawdust), S₄ (S₁ with 5% oyster shell meal and 5% sawdust) and S₅ (uncultivated forest soil). Four diets including two industrial (D₁ and D₂ of 12% and 16% calcium respectively) and two based on fodder (D₃ and D₄ based on leaves and fruit of the papaya (*Carica papaya*) on the one hand and a mixture of papaya leaves and taro (*Xanthosoma maffafa*) on the other hand, were used. In order to determine the best combinations inducing the best growth performance, 20 combinations were formed at the rate of 45 spat for each combination; three replicas of 15 spat each. This study showed that the combination of diet and livestock substrate influences the growth of *Archachatina marginata*. Although the best feed is D₁ (74.68 g and 7.94cm) and the best substrate is S₂ (77.12 g and 7.79cm), the best combinations are D₂S₃ (69.37 g and 7.47cm), D₁S₄ (74.68 g and 7.94cm and D₄S₂ (77.12 g and 7.79cm). The combined effect of the high level of dietary calcium and that of the culture substrate does not promote good growth of snails. This work will help improve the production of African giant snails and provide important data for anyone wishing to engage in the breeding of these animals.

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Introduction

Naturally available food resources play a fairly substantial role in populations (Sodjinou *et al.*, 2002). Among these resources, African giant snails (or Achatines) belonging to the family Achatinidae are found there. These snails are highly valued by many African populations (Zongo 1995). For example, Achatine meat is the most consumed meat in South Benin ahead of aulacode, chicken, sheep or goats, beef and pork (Sodjinou *et al.*, 2002). It is estimated that in Côte d'Ivoire, the population eats 7.9 million kg of snails per year, while in Ghana; demand clearly exceeds production capacity (Cobbinah *et al.*, 2008).

Unfortunately, these protein resources are becoming scarce in their natural environment. To compensate for these deficits, heliciculture is one of the alternatives to diversify the sources of animal protein of populations. It is therefore right that initiatives to breed these animals should be carried out in order to satisfy the ever-increasing demand for their consumption, but also to ensure the sustainability of the resource. Thus, several research initiatives on the pace of activity, growth (Ejidike *et al.*, Otchoumou *et al.*, 2004; Kouassi *et al.*, 2016), on reproduction (Otchoumou *et al.*, 2005, Kouassi, 2008) as well as on snail farming substrate were supported (Kouassi *et al.*, 2016; Awohouedji *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, the success of such breeding goes beyond the control of the feed, the breeding substrate, the pathology of these animals, but also and above all by a healthy appreciation of the food according to the different types of breeding substrate. Thus, the substrate is a key element for snails as it is both a source of mineral nutrients and a refuge.

In terms of snail production, several studies have shown the effect of feeding (Kouassi *et al.*, 2007, Kouassi, 2002) or farming substrate on the growth and reproduction of these animals by a variation in calcium levels. However, to our knowledge, no studies have yet been devoted to the combined effect of diet and substrate. The objective of this study is to highlight the combined effect of diet and culture substrate on the live weight and growth of the shell of

Archachatina marginata in order to optimize its rearing. It was therefore necessary to evaluate the combined effect of food and substrate on the weight and shell growth of snails.

Material and method

Study site and animals

This study took place at the school-farm of Jean Lorougnon Guedé University, Côte d'Ivoire from September 2021 to February 2022; i.e a duration of 24 weeks. The average temperature and relative humidity of the rearing environment are respectively $25.5 \pm 2.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $90.7 \pm 3.8\%$.

The biological material used in this study consists of snails belonging to a single species (Fig. 1): *Archachatina marginata* (Swainson, 1821). They were born at the farm-school of Jean Lorougnon Guedé University from breeders collected in the South Comoé region, Ivory Coast. About two weeks old, they are free of trauma (shell well formed, well filled and without breakage) and have an average live weight of 2.25 ± 0.1 g for an average shell length of 20.12 ± 0.5 mm.

Fig. 1. *Archachatina marginata*.

Breeding substrates

Five types of substrates were used for this study. The first, S₁ is the superficial layer (from 0 to 40cm deep) of the soil of a cassava plantation (*Manihot* sp.), a tuber widely cultivated in Côte d'Ivoire. The choice of this soil is linked to the fact that the breeding of snails will only be done on soils already exploited and certainly by the practice of cassava cultivation. The second substrate (S₂) is a mixture of 90% of the S₁ substrate and 10% of oyster shell flour (Table 1). The third, (S₃) is a mixture of 90% S₁ and 10% sawdust of wood. The fourth, (S₄) is a mixture of 90% S₁ with 5% oyster shell flour and 5% sawdust of wood. Substrate S₅ is the superficial layer (from 0 to 40cm deep) of the soil of a fallow forest at Jean Lorougnon Guedé University, control soil.

Foods

Four types of food were used in this study. The first two (D₁ and D₂) are industrial foods formulated in the form of flour with varying levels of calcium (Table 2). The D₃ and D₄ diets are composed of chlorophyllous foods. They are the result of a mixture of papaya leaves and fruits (*Carica papaya*) on the one hand (D₃) and a mixture of papaya leaves and *Xanthosoma maffafa* leaves on the other hand (diet D₄).

Methodology

A total of 900 *A. marginata* juveniles were used in this study which lasted 24 weeks; from September 2020 to February 2021. Sixty batches of 15 snails each were formed for all 20 combinations (4 diets x 5 substrates), i.e three repetitions per combination. These batches are placed in brick bins with area is 1 m² for 0.5 m³ of volume (Fig. 2) to assess zootechnical performance related to food and/or rearing substrate. Fitted with a mosquito net-type lid constituting the anti-leakage device and allowing the animals to ventilate, the interior of the bins is made up of various substrates prepared for this purpose at a thickness of 10cm. The animals are regularly watered and fed ad libitum every two days. Every two weeks, they are weighed using an electronic pocket scale of 0.01 g precision. Shell length is determined using a 0.01mm precision electronic caliper and mortality is also noted.

Fig. 2. Breeding pen.

Chemical analysis

The substrates used in this study were the subject of a chemical analysis by SODEMI (Société pour le Développement Minier de la Côte d'Ivoire). Minerals such as iron, aluminum, calcium and magnesium were determined by the method of chemical determination of oxides of major elements. Copper and zinc were determined by the determination of base metals using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The organic matter of the substrates was dissolved in 50% hydrogen peroxide and the different proportions were determined according to the formula $[(Pi - Pf) \times 100 / Pi]$.

with:

Pi= weight in grams of the dry sample before treatment with hydrogen peroxide.

Pf= weight in grams of the dry sample after treatment with hydrogen peroxide

Statistical analyzes and expression of results

The R software and Microsoft Excel 2007 made it possible to carry out the various statistical treatments. Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the value of foods and substrates. As for the R software, it was used to discriminate between the different combinations of rearing substrates and food. The weight and shellfish growths are estimated from the average daily growth every two weeks and expressed by the average weight growth (g/d), the average shellfish growth (mm/d). Cumulative mortality is also calculated according to the formulas:

Average weight gain (CP)

$$CP = \frac{Pf - Pi}{Tf - Ti} \quad (1)$$

Pi: Initial average live weight
 Pf: Final average live weight
 Ti: Initial time in days
 Tf: Final time in days

Average shellfish growth (CC)

$$CC = \frac{L_f - L_i}{T_f - T_i} \quad (2)$$

Li: Mean initial shell length
 Lf: Mean final shell length

The cumulative mortality rate (MC) is obtained according to the formula

$$MC = \frac{Nam}{Nta} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Nam: Total number of dead animals
 Nta: Total number of animals experimented

Results

Composition of rearing substrates and nutritional value of feed

The chemical analysis of the different substrates (Table 1) indicates that the substrates are rich in aluminum oxide (3.43-4.57%) and iron oxide (2.68-3.31%). On the other hand, the substrates are poor in copper (trace), in zinc (0.003-0.004%) and in magnesium oxide (0.03-0.09%). The rates of calcium oxide and organic matter are variable respectively between 0.04 and 4.6% and between 1.21 and 10.81%. The S₂ substrate is the richest in calcium oxide while the S₃ substrate is the richest in organic matter.

Table 1. Composition of substrates Tableau.

Component	Substrate 1 (S ₁)	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅
Cultivated ground	100	90	90	90	0
Forest ground	0	0	0	0	100
Powder of oyster	0	10	0	5	0
Sawdust	0	0	10	5	0
Chimic analysis					
AlO ₃	4,57	4,32	4,3	4,26	3,43
Fe ₂ O ₃	3,31	2,82	3,32	2,92	2,68
CaO	0,08	4,6	0,12	2,48	0,04
MgO	0,04	0,09	0,04	0,07	0,03
Zn	0,003	0,004	0,004	0,004	0,004
Cu	Trace	Trace	Trace	Trace	Trace
Organic matter	1,22	1,21	10,81	5,68	6,04

The nutritional value of the foods used in this study (Table 2) reveals that the D₁ and D₂ foods produced in the laboratory have a high rate of minerals (38.43 and 43.35%) than the D₃ and D₄ foods composed of leaves and fruits (2.37 & 11.15%).

The levels of phosphorus (0.1 to 1.2%), potassium (0.82 to 1.08%), sodium (0.34 to 0.52) and cellulose (2.41 to 4.76) are more or less of the same order in all foods. On the other hand, the levels of calcium (0.33 to 16.01%), protein (4.67 to 17.48%) and fat (1.5 to 4.71%) vary greatly from one food to the other.

Table 2. Composition of the experimental diet.

Ingredients	Diet 1 (D1)	Diet 2 (D2)	Diet 3 (D3)	Diet 4 (D4)
Fresh pawpaw leaves	0	0	50	50
Fresh xanthosoma leaves	0	0	50	0
Fruit of pawpaw	0	0	0	50
maize	19,3	9,7	0	0
Coton	16	15,7	0	0
Soja graine	16	15,7	0	0
Blé tendre	15	14,7	0	0
Phosphate of calcium	4	4	0	0
Complexe of vitamins	0,5	0,5	0	0
Powder of shell oyster	28,7	39,2	0	0
NaCl	0,1	0,1	0	0
Oligot-elements	0,4	0,4	0	0
Total (g)	100	100	100	100
Analysis content				
Ash	38,43	43,35	2,37	11,15
Ca	12,02	16,01	0,33	0,84
Phosphore	1,2	1,19	0,71	0,1
Potassium	1,02	1,04	0,82	1,08
Sodium	0,37	0,34	0,47	0,52
Crude cellulose	4,76	4,67	2,41	2,53
Protein	17,48	17,14	4,67	5,67
Fat	4,71	4,61	1,5	1,83

Feeding and growth of A. marginata

The Figures of plate 1: a₁, b₁, c₁, d₁, and e₁ on the one hand and a₂, b₂, c₂, d₂ and e₂ on the other hand, show respectively the weight growth and the shell growth of the snail *Archachatina marginata* submitted to four types of food according to the different substrates. The effect induced by food on the weight and shell growth of *A. marginata* snails is revealing and variable from one substrate to another.

The analysis of these graphs shows that on substrates poor in calcium (S₁, S₃ and S₅), the best foods are those which are rich in calcium (D₁ and D₂). On the other hand, on S₂ and S₄ substrates, rich in calcium, the best foods are D₁. & D₄.

Basic statistics reveal that the best food among those tested is food D₁ (Table 3). Food D₁ induced the best average weight and shell growth (26.03 g and 4.83cm) followed by D₂ (21.07 g and 4.63cm), D₄ (18.84 g and 4.01cm) and D₃ (15.87 g and 4.07cm).

Statistical analysis by comparing the average weight and shell growths induced reveals a significant difference between food D₁ and foods D₃ and D₄. There is, however, no statistical difference between D₁

and D₂, as well as between D₃ and D₄. The average mortality is relatively low and is between 0.48% (food D₃) and 0.18% (food D₁). Animals subjected to D₃ recorded the highest mortality rate (0.48%).

Table 3. Elementary statistics relating to the diet.

	Live weight				Shell length				Mortality			
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D1	D2	D3	D4	D1	D2	D3	D4
Number of data	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Mean	26,03 ^a	21,07 ^{ab}	15,87 ^b	18,05 ^b	4,83 ^a	4,63 ^a	4,07 ^b	4,01 ^b	0,18 ^b	0,22 ^b	0,48 ^a	0,2 ^b
Standard deviation	18,74	14,76	12,76	18,84	1,61	1,35	1,24	1,51	0,43	0,48	0,85	0,51
Minimum	1,76	1,78	1,8	1,67	2,01	2	2	1,97	0	0	0	0
Maximum	74,68	69,37	59,23	77,12	7,94	7,47	7,06	7,79	2	2	3	2

The mean of the same growth parameter indexed by the same letter are not statistically different (p<0,05)

Fig. 2. Effect of the rearing substrate on the weight and shell growth of *A. marginata*.

Breeding substrate and growth of A. marginata

In order to ensure the effect induced by the breeding substrate on the growth of snails, the weight and shell growth of *A. marginata* was evaluated according to five types of substrates (Plate 2). Weight growth (a_3 , b_3 , c_3 and d_3) and shell growth (Fig. a_4 , b_4 , c_4 and d_4) varies from one substrate to another. The temporal analysis of the different graphs indicates a clear demarcation between the substrates when the animals are subjected to vegetarian diets. The best substrates that emerge from this are S_2 and S_4 . On the other hand, the S_3 substrate, rich in organic matter, appears to be the best when the snails are fed with the D_2 food having the highest calcium content.

The best substrates are in the order of S_2 (25.59 g and 4.8cm) > S_4 (24.46 g and 4.76cm) > S_3 (20.41 g and 4.31cm) > S_5 (16.03 g and 4.07cm) > S_1 (14.80 g and 3.99cm) (Table 4). The comparison of the means with the R software reveals a statistical difference between the growth of the snails reared on substrate S_2 and those reared on S_1 and S_5 . However, there is no difference in growth between the animals of the S_2 , S_3 and S_4 substrates. Also, the cumulative average mortality of snails reared on S_1 (0.5%) and S_5 (0.62%) substrates seems high compared to that of animals on S_4 (0%), S_3 (0.21%) substrates. and S_2 (0.02). The lowest mortality was recorded on the S_4 substrate (0%).

Table 4. Statistiques élémentaires relatives au substrat.

	Live weight					Shell length					Mortality				
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
Number of data	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
Mean	14,8 ^b	25,59 ^a	20,41 ^{ab}	24,46 ^a	16,03 ^b	3,99 ^b	4,8 ^a	4,31 ^{ab}	4,76 ^a	4,07 ^b	0,5 ^a	0,02 ^{bc}	0,21 ^b	0 ^c	0,62 ^a
Standar deviation	9,94	20	17,6	19,6	12,3	1,11	1,7	1,44	1,7	1,26	0,8	0,14	0,6	0	0,79
Minimum	1,77	1,77	1,67	1,98	2,24	1,98	2	1,97	2	2;11	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum	35,6	77,12	69,47	74,7	49,9	5,88	7,8	7,47	7,9	6,81	3	1	2	0	3

Fig. 1. Effect of the diet on the weight and shell growth of *A. marginata*.

Interaction between food and rearing substrates on the growth of A. marginata

The characteristics of the growth of *Archahchatina marginata* under the combined effect of food and rearing substrate are recorded in Table 5.

A careful analysis of this table reveals that after six months, the final weight and shell length of the snails vary respectively between 15.7 g (D_3S_5) and 77.12 g (D_4S_2) and between 4.3cm (D_3S_5) and 7.94cm (D_1S_4) for an average mass between 8.86 g (D_4S_1) and 32.96 g (D_2S_3). Daily weight gain fluctuates between 0.08 g/d (D_3S_5) and 0.49 g/d (D_4S_2). As for shellfish growth, it fluctuates between 0.013cm/d (D_3S_5) and

0.035cm/d D₁S₄). The four best weight increases were obtained in order with the combinations: D₄S₂ (0.449 g/d), D₁S₄ (0.434 g/d), D₂S₃ (0.397 g/d), and D₄S₄ (0.384 g/d). On the other hand, the best shell growth was obtained in the order of the combinations D₁S₄ (0.035cm/d), D₄S₂ (0.034cm/d), D₄S₄ (0.032cm/d) and D₂S₃ (0.031cm/d). Thus, out of a total of 20 combinations, four turn out to be more favorable for

good snail growth. The combinations not favorable to good snail growth are in the order of D₃S₅ (0.080 g/d and 0.013cm/d), D₄S₁ (0.090 g/d and 0.015cm/d), D₄S₃ (0.106 g/d and 0.016cm/d), D₃S₁ (0.110 g/d and 0.016cm/d) and D₃S₃ (0.127 g/d and 0.016cm/d). These combinations are characterized by an absence of minerals, in particular calcium, both in the feed and in the substrate.

Table 5. Parameters of growth according to combinations diet & substrate.

	Parameters								
	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Average weight (g)	Daily average ponderal growth (g/day)	Initial length of shell (cm)	Final length of shell (cm)	Average length of shell (cm)	Daily average shell growth (cm/day)	Average mortality (%)
D ₁ S ₁	2.33 ^a	34.33 ^{gh}	19.58 ^{cdef}	0.190 ^{fghi}	2.20 ^a	5.38 ^{efgh}	4.28 ^{abcdef}	0.010 ^{bcdef}	0.154 ^{cd}
D ₁ S ₂	2.47 ^a	54.93 ^{de}	28.85 ^{abc}	0.312 ^{bcde}	2.23 ^a	7.14 ^{abcd}	5.16 ^a	0.029 ^{abcde}	0.000 ^d
D ₁ S ₃	2.50 ^a	54.13 ^{de}	26.17 ^{abc}	0.307 ^{cde}	2.29 ^a	6.33 ^{bcdef}	4.66 ^{abcd}	0.024 ^{abcdef}	0.154 ^{cd}
D ₁ S ₄	1.76 ^a	74.68 ^{ab}	32.18 ^a	0.434 ^{ab}	2.01 ^a	7.94 ^a	5.29 ^a	0.035 ^a	0.000 ^d
D ₁ S ₅	2.25 ^a	49.90 ^{ef}	23.37 ^{abcde}	0.284 ^{def}	2.20 ^a	6.81 ^{abcde}	4.76 ^{abc}	0.027 ^{abcdef}	0.615 ^b
D ₂ S ₁	2.25 ^a	30.08 ^h	19.24 ^{cdef}	0.166 ^{ghij}	2.20 ^a	5.65 ^{defgh}	4.54 ^{abcd}	0.021 ^{abcdef}	0.462 ^{bc}
D ₂ S ₂	2.40 ^a	32.78 ^{gh}	14.94 ^{def}	0.181 ^{fghi}	2.20 ^a	5.75 ^{defgh}	4.41 ^{abcde}	0.021 ^{abcdef}	0.077 ^{cd}
D ₂ S ₃	2.73 ^a	69.37 ^{bc}	32.96 ^a	0.397 ^{abc}	2.33 ^a	7.47 ^{ab}	5.32 ^a	0.031 ^{abcd}	0.231 ^{bcd}
D ₂ S ₄	1.78 ^a	30.68 ^h	17.20 ^{def}	0.172 ^{ghij}	2.00 ^a	5.93 ^{cdefg}	4.39 ^{abcdef}	0.023 ^{abcdef}	0.000 ^d
D ₂ S ₅	2.25 ^a	36.53 ^g	18.02 ^{def}	0.204 ^{fgh}	2.15 ^a	5.80 ^{defgh}	4.47 ^{abcde}	0.022 ^{abcdef}	0.308 ^{bcd}
D ₃ S ₁	2.38 ^a	20.80 ^{ij}	11.52 ^f	0.110 ^{hij}	2.23 ^a	4.92 ^{fgh}	3.77 ^{cdef}	0.016 ^{def}	1.077 ^a
D ₃ S ₂	2.50 ^a	59.23 ^d	24.57 ^{abcd}	0.338 ^{bcd}	2.25 ^a	7.06 ^{abcd}	4.7 ^{abc}	0.029 ^{abcde}	0.000 ^d
D ₃ S ₃	2.50 ^a	23.83 ⁱ	12.99 ^{ef}	0.127 ^{hij}	2.30 ^a	4.95 ^{fgh}	3.86 ^{bcdef}	0.016 ^{def}	0.154 ^{cd}
D ₃ S ₄	1.80 ^a	44.85 ^f	20.86 ^{bcdef}	0.256 ^{efg}	2.00 ^a	6.54 ^{abcde}	4.54 ^{abcd}	0.027 ^{abcdef}	0.000 ^d
D ₃ S ₅	2.33 ^a	15.70 ^j	9.43 ^f	0.080 ^j	2.15 ^a	4.30 ^h	3.47 ^{ef}	0.013 ^f	1.154 ^a
D ₄ S ₁	1.77 ^a	16.86 ^j	8.86 ^f	0.090 ^{ij}	1.98 ^a	4.42 ^h	3.34 ^f	0.015 ^{def}	0.308 ^{bcd}
D ₄ S ₂	1.77 ^a	77.12 ^a	30.98 ^{ab}	0.449 ^a	2.02 ^a	7.79 ^{ab}	4.92 ^{ab}	0.034 ^{ab}	0.000 ^d
D ₄ S ₃	1.74 ^a	19.57 ^{ij}	9.51 ^f	0.106 ^{ij}	1.97 ^a	4.6 ^{gh}	3.41 ^{ef}	0.016 ^{def}	0.308 ^{bcd}
D ₄ S ₄	1.75 ^a	66.22 ^c	27.61 ^{abc}	0.384 ^{abcd}	1.98 ^a	7.35 ^{abc}	4.81 ^{abc}	0.032 ^{abc}	0.000 ^d
D ₄ S ₅	2.24 ^a	29.52 ^h	13.31 ^{def}	0.162 ^{ghij}	2.11 ^a	5.02 ^{fgh}	3.60 ^{def}	0.017 ^{cdef}	0.385 ^{bcd}

The mean of the same growth parameter indexed by the same letter are not statistically different (p<0,05)

The average mortality of the different combinations varies little; between 0% and 1.15%. The highest mortalities were recorded on the D₃S₅ (1.15%) and D₃S₁ (1.08%) combinations

Discussion

Food influences the growth of snails, as evidenced by the results of this study. Also, it emerges from this study that the best foods inducing good growth of snails are industrial foods in the form of flour: D₁ with 12% calcium and D₂ composed of 16% calcium. Indeed, in order to optimize the growth performance of snails, several food preparation initiatives have been initiated (Zongo *et al.*, 1990). Thus, foods D₁ and D₂ have been enriched with nutrients, in particular dietary calcium, and induce good growth in snails. On

the other hand, snails are vegetarians in the wild and must seek their nutrients necessary for their growth in several sources. This justifies the weak growth observed in animals fed with a reduced number of plants; here papaya leaves and fruits (*Carica papyra*) and taro leaves (*Xanthosoma maffafa*). The results of this study also show that the growth of snails is influenced by the breeding substrate. These results are in agreement with those of Graham, (1978) and Jess and Mark, (1989), who report that the soil not only constitutes a real refuge for snails, but the latter draw about 40% of their nutrients from it. The performances observed seem to be strongly linked to the level of calcium and magnesium. Indeed, the best snail growth was obtained on S₂ and S₄ substrates, rich in calcium and magnesium.

These results agree with those of Chevalier, (1992) and Ebenso, (2003) who noted that snails like ferralitic and/or limestone soils rich in water. Also, magnesium is involved in several essential enzymatic reactions, in particular in the production of energy. It acts in balance with other minerals, such as calcium or potassium (Graham, 1978).

Although food D₁ and substrate S₂ are the best food and substrate in the present study, the best combinations inducing good growth of snails are D₁S₄, D₂S₃, D₄S₂ and D₄S₄ and not D₁S₂. This result suggests an interaction between the minerals of the substrate and those of the food in the sense of a complementation of the rate of dietary calcium and that of the substrate. Feed with high calcium content (16%) is compatible with a substrate rich in organic matter (D₂S₃) and feed with moderate calcium content (12%) is better suited to a substrate with moderate calcium content; witness the growth observed at the level of the D₁S₄ and D₄S₂ combinations. This complementation seems to admit a limit beyond which the calcium content proves to be toxic or inhibiting the growth of *A. marginata* (D₂S₂, combination rich in calcium but inducing weak growth 14.94g and 4.41cm). These results are in agreement with those of Aman, (2011) and Bouye, (2017), which limit the calcium level of substrate amendment to 6.23% for a diet of 12% calcium. In addition, our results indicate better daily growth performance in *A. marginanta* than conventional above-ground breeding in buildings or under shade without calcium amendment of the substrate. Indeed, after 24 weeks of experimentation, the D₁S₄, D₂S₃, D₄S₂ and D₄S₄ combinations gave better weight and shellfish growth than those obtained by Kouassi and Aman, (2014), certainly thanks to the combined effect of food nutrients and those of the rearing substrate. Also, daily weight and shellfish growths are better than those obtained by Otchoumou *et al.*, (2003) on substrates amended with different sources of calcium.

Conclusion

The study on the interaction of diet and culture substrate on the growth of *Archachatina marginata* snails in the rearing environment revealed that a

calcium-rich feed is suitable for better growth of snails on a substrate rich in organic matter. On the other hand, on a substrate rich in calcium, a plant-based diet (low in calcium) is needed for good growth of snails. The accumulation of calcium in the feed and in the substrate is to be avoided in the case of the breeding of giant snails because inhibits the growth of these animals.

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